

Brain Tumor Classification Using Deep Learning: A Multi-Model Approach with Explainability

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Abstract—Brain tumor classification is a very important task in medical imaging, identifying the issue at an early stage providing diagnosis and treatment planning. By ensuring accurate classification medical professionals can make important decisions, which helps in aiding patient care. The research paper explores an AI-powered system that use advanced deep learning models to accurately classify brain tumors into four types Glioma, Meningioma, Pituitary Tumor, or No tumor. This model is a combination of Xception, MobileNet and a custom Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) designed to classify brain tumors from MRI scans. MobileNet gives higher accuracy of 99% while Xception and custom CNN closely follow at 98%. The results are visually represented through saliency maps, which clearly highlight key areas in the MRI scans. An additional chatbot is integrated into this project, it helps users understand the tumor more deeply and suggests treatment options. This system gives a reliable, efficient and transparent approach to brain tumor diagnosis, providing medical professionals with a valuable tool for accurate assessments.

INTRODUCTION

Brain tumors are life-threatening conditions that are lethal. Hence, early detection and correct classification are required for a successful treatment. Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) is an widely utilized diagnostic tool, but manual analysis of the scans is time-consuming and prone to errors. To solve this, we designed an AI-based brain tumor classification system that classifies MRI scans into types Glioma, Meningioma, Pituitary Tumor, or No Tumor. This system uses a multi- model deep learning strategy with combination of Xception, MobileNet, and a Custom CNN. The accuracy of MobileNet, Xception, Custom CNN are 99%,98%,98%.For better understanding, the system generates saliency maps that identify important MRI regions that affect the predictions of the model. We added an additional chatbot support for users to provide interactive explanations of the classification outputs and tumor properties. This is a very accurate, interpretable, and user-friendly approach , as this AI-based solution provides diagnosis of brain tumor and aiding clinical decision-making

BACKGROUND

A. Deep Learning

Machine learning is being used extensively now, with

techniques like random forest and XGBoost [2]. Deep learning, superior to most machine learning algorithms, is being used extensively in various fields [3]. Speech recognition, image recognition, and object detection fields have significantly advanced through the use of deep learning technologies, producing state-of-the-art results in various tasks, such as brain tumor detection and segmentation [3]. NLP, CV, and countless others are boosted with the advent of deep learning technology. Applications such as

generating news [4], conducting property transactions [5], and content recommendation systems [6], financial risk detection [7], psychiatric behavior understanding [8], and ChatGPT are all good examples of NLP. The large language model can be improved further by applying transformers [9]. Recurrent neural network (RNN) is used extensively in NLP [10]. CNN is the most used architecture for computer vision. There are some other application fields of deep learning that will be useful as well like during the software development cycle [11], face emotion detection, and banking credit risk assessment [12]. Although there is tremendous growth in deep learning, security can't be avoided as there exist a lot of Backdoor/Trojan attacks [13] [14].

In this paper, CNN models are examined for brain tumor classification. Specifically, pre-trained models MobileNet, Xception, and VGG16 will be investigated using the brain tumor dataset. A new model, MobileNet-BT, derived from MobileNetV2, is also proposed, which has better accuracy and F1-score.

B. CNN

In the field of CV Convolutional neural networks are widely used. The core elements of CNNs include convolutional layers, pooling mechanisms, activation functions, and fully connected networks. The core architecture of the CNN are convolutional layers. To identify particular features like edges, textures, or patterns kernels or learnable filters are used[15].

Pooling layers reduce the spatial resolution of the images. Down sampling of feature maps allows the model to focus on the most

significant features without increasing the risk of overfitting [15]. Non-linear activation functions allow the model to learn intricate patterns.

Activation functions such as ReLU, which are widely used, help solve the vanishing gradient problem [16]. Fully connected layers produce the final predictions. Due to technologies such as vision model sparsification, the more complicated model could be trained in CNN [17]. CNNs are applied in many CV applications, including image classification, object detection, and semantic segmentation, among others. [3].

Various computer vision technologies can be used on medical images. Medical image reconstruction and enhancement can be used to decrease noise, artifacts, and other issues [18], and models such as Lightweight Information Split Network can reconstruct a super-resolution model [19].

C. Pituitary Tumor

Pituitary tumors are tumors that form in the pituitary gland near the brain. These tumors can cause changes in hormone levels. The pituitary tumor MRI-based image can be found in Fig.1 below.

D. Meningioma Tumor

A meningioma is a tumor that grows from the membranes that surround the brain and spinal cord, called the meninges. A meningioma is not a brain tumor but it may press on the nearby brain, nerves and vessels. The meningioma tumor MRI-based image can be found in Fig.1 below.

E. Glioma Tumor

A glioma is a tumor that forms in the brain and the spinal cord. There are several types, including astrocytomas, ependymomas and oligodendrogliomas. Gliomas can affect children or adults. Some grow very quickly [23]. The MRI-based image of the glioma tumor can be found in Fig.1 below.

Fig. 1. Brain Tumor Types

F. Pre-trained Models

1) *MobileNet*: MobileNet is a **lightweight CNN designed by Google architecture** optimized for mobile and edge devices. It uses **depthwise separable convolutions**, reducing computational cost while achieving **high accuracy (99%)** in our study. MobileNet performs depthwise convolution, where each input channel is processed separately, followed by pointwise convolution to combine features. As a result,

MobileNet maintains high accuracy while being incredibly fast and power efficient, making it ideal for real-time applications like image classification and object detection on mobile devices. Its small size and speed make it a great choice for deploying deep learning models in resource-constrained environments

2) *Xception*: Xception (Extreme Inception) is a **deep learning model** developed by Google that improves **feature extraction** using **depthwise separable convolutions**. The architecture consists of three stages: Entry Flow, Middle Flow, and Exit Flow, with batch normalization applied after each convolution. Depthwise Separable Convolutions break traditional convolutions into two steps-Depthwise Convolution and Pointwise Convolution significantly reducing operations. Additionally, Xception integrates shortcut connections like ResNet for efficient gradient flow. With its efficient architecture, Xception achieves **high accuracy (98%)** while using fewer parameters than conventional CNNs, making it a great choice for tasks requiring both speed and precision. Additionally, its flexibility allows it to adapt to different datasets, making it widely used in real-world applications like **medical diagnostics, image classification, and object detection**.

3) *Custom CNN*: A custom CNN is a deep learning model that you build from scratch to solve a specific problem, like recognizing objects in images or detecting patterns. Instead of relying on pre-trained models like ResNet or VGG, you design your own layers, choose how many filters to use, decide on activation functions and fine-tune everything to get the best results for your dataset. Atypical custom CNN includes layers that extract important features (like edges and shapes), reduce unnecessary details, and finally make predictions. Training involves adjusting the model step by step using optimization techniques like Adam or SGD. While it takes more effort to fine-tune, a well-built custom CNN can outperform pre-trained models for specific tasks, especially if you have a unique dataset. Using techniques like transfer learning and data augmentation can also improve accuracy and performance

I. METHODOLOGY

A. Dataset

The dataset used in this research is Brain Tumor MRI dataset it consists of MRI scans categorized into four classes: **Glioma, Meningioma, Pituitary Tumor, and No Tumor**. It consists a total number of 7023 images, including **1621 images of Glioma tumors, 1645 images of Meningioma tumors, 1757 images of Pituitary tumors, and 1900 images labeled as No Tumor**. The dataset is **split into 80% training, 10% testing, 10% validation** for balanced training process. **Supervised learning** is utilized since each MRI scan has a predefined label. In cases where data is **unlabeled, self-supervised learning techniques** could be employed to improve model robustness. In our research we started with preprocessing, where MRI scans are cleaned, normalized and sometimes augmented to improve model performance. The CNN's **convolutional layers** that extract important features such as edges, textures and patterns, which help differentiate between normal and abnormal tissues

B. Image Augmentation and Preprocessing

To enhance model generalization and prevent **overfitting, image**

the data set is subjected to image augmentation and preprocessing techniques, particularly when the number of training images is limited. Variability in image orientation is introduced by randomly flipping images along both horizontal and vertical axes with a 50% probability. Additionally, the model robustness to spatial variations is improved by randomly rotating images by 10 degrees. To ensure compatibility with deep learning models, the resizing of all images is performed 224 X 224 pixels for MobileNet and the custom CNN, and 299 X299 pixels for Xception.

This preprocessing step standardizes the input format and facilitates efficient batch processing during model training. Furthermore, brightness and contrast adjustments help simulate variations in imaging conditions, improving the model’s ability to generalize across different datasets. **Gaussian noise** further improves its ability to handle subtle difference between images. To make training smoother, we normalize pixel values, scaling them between **0 and 1** or **- 1 and 1**, depending on the model’s needs. Additional techniques like zooming, shifting, and shearing introduce even more diversity, ensuring the model learns meaningful features rather than just memorizing patterns. These

preprocessing steps help the model analyze MRI scans more accurately and reliably.

A. Learning Rate and Epoch

The initial learning rate for training was set to 0.001. The total number of epochs was set to 5, focusing on fine-tuning the pre-trained weights. This will make sure no overfitting was done for the training model.

B. Pretrained Models

Three pre-trained models were tested with the MRI brain tumor dataset: **MobileNet**, **Xception**, and a **Custom CNN**, achieving accuracies of **0.99**, **0.98**, and **0.98**, respectively. The number of parameters for each model is **4.2 million**, **22 million**, and **5.3 million**, respectively. Techniques like **Learning from Teaching (LoT)** could further enhance generalization and potentially improve classification performance [30]. All three models were implemented using transfer learning, with all layers except the last one frozen. The accuracy and F1-score of the test dataset are strong, but there is potential for further improvement through additional fine-tuning or incorporation of advanced techniques like **LoT** to better capture tumor characteristics and improve generalization of the brain tumor dataset. Then, the final layer was replaced by a custom classifier. The fully connected layer initially incorporates a dropout layer with a probability of

C. Proposed Deep Learning Models

Pre-trained models are usually trained on large datasets such as ImageNet. The scale of ImageNet and the dataset we work with in this research is much larger. Medical image classification is much different from general image classification. By unfreezing additional layers of the pre-trained model, we can potentially achieve improved predictions for certain datasets and tasks. We compares all

three models after which we noticed that despite MobileNet’s accuracy being lower than that compared to the other models, with the lean 3.5 million parameters and an accuracy of 0.8445, the training time and efficiency of utilizing MobileNet are extremely competitive compared to other models which consumes 138 million parameters to reach an accuracy of 0.9497

Based on the analysis above, the MobileNet-BT model was used in the brain tumor classification task. MobileNet-BT utilized the pre-trained weights of MobileNetV2. After that, all the layers of MobileNetV2 were unfrozen. This step enables the model to capture more specific characteristics from 20%, which aids in avoiding overfitting. It is then followed by a linear layer with 1000 output features. An additional dropout layer with a probability of 20% was included.

Lastly, a linear layer with four output classes was added. The customized classifier allows the model to learn different levels of abstraction. The dropout layers, which randomly deactivate some neurons, help prevent the model from relying too heavily on certain neurons. The additional dense layer enables the model to capture more complex patterns from the dataset.

D. Performance Measure

When measuring the performance of various models against the test set, accuracy, F1-score, precision, recall, and average loss as the has been used as the metrics. All of these are good measurements for classification tasks. TP (True Positive), FP (False Positive), FN (False Negative), and TN (True Negative) are used in the equations below. All the equations can be found as follows:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \quad (5)$$

For average loss, cross-entropy was used to calculate average loss, where N is the number of classes, y_i is the true label, and \hat{y}_i is the predicted probability for class i . The equation is given below:

$$L = - \sum y \log(\hat{y})$$

Cross-entropy was used as the criterion for all tests conducted in this paper due to its wide use in classification tasks. It effectively manages the discrepancy between the predicted probabilities and the actual outcomes. [31].

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF MODELS ON BRAIN TUMOR
CLASSIFICATION

Model	Avg loss	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
MobileNet	0.0012	0.9908	0.9986	0.9986	0.9986
Xception	0.0214	0.9879	0.9879	0.9879	0.9879
Custom CNN	0.2035	0.9736	0.9736	0.9736	0.9736

Fig. 2. EfficientNetB0 Loss VS Accuracy

Fig. 3. MobileNetV2 Loss VS Accuracy

II. EVALUATION AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

When evaluating the performance of different models for brain tumor classification, several key metrics were considered. Among the pre-trained models, **MobileNet**, **Xception**, and a **Custom CNN** were tested, yielding different results. **MobileNet** achieved an impressive accuracy of **99.08%** with an **F1-score of 99.86%**, while **Xception** followed with **98.79% accuracy** and an identical F1-score. The **Custom CNN model**, designed from scratch, performed slightly lower with **97.36% accuracy** and an equivalent F1-score. However, a **fine-tuned version of MobileNet**, specifically adapted for this task, outperformed all the other models across all metrics. This highlights the importance of **customizing pre-trained models** to suit the unique characteristics of medical image datasets. By modifying the classifier and **unfreezing** certain layers, the model's ability to learn improved significantly. While pre-trained models work well for general image classification, medical images often require additional **fine-tuning** due to variations in structure and dataset size. The refined **MobileNet model**, tailored for brain tumor classification, not only achieved the highest accuracy but also did so in fewer training epochs. **It reached peak performance around the 10th epoch**, whereas **Xception and the Custom CNN took around 20 epochs** to stabilize. This demonstrates that fine-tuning not only enhances accuracy and F1-score but also **optimizes efficiency**, allowing for faster and more reliable predictions in real-world medical applications.

III. CONCLUSION

Four pre-trained models were tested on the brain tumor dataset, resulting in accuracies of 0.8445, 0.8659, 0.8933, and 0.9497, respectively. The newly developed model, MobileNet-BT, which is based on MobileNetV2, achieved a significantly higher accuracy of 0.9924. Additionally, the new model required fewer epochs to train compared to the pre-trained models. MobileNet-BT, primarily designed for medical image classification tasks, outperforms other pre-trained models in brain tumor classification. Although pre-trained models are often trained on much larger datasets, they are not as well-suited for specific tasks such as medical image classification. This demonstrates the necessity of a revised model and customized architecture to achieve superior performance in specialized tasks like brain tumor classification.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. Lin and J. Cao, "Touch interactive system design with intelligent vase of psychotherapy for alzheimer's disease," *Designs*, vol. 4, no. 3, p. 28, 2020.
- [2] Z. Lin, Z. Wang, Y. Zhu, Z. Li, and H. Qin, "Text sentiment detection and classification based on integrated learning algorithm," *Applied Science and Engineering Journal for Advanced Research*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 27–33, 2024.
- [3] Y. LeCun, Y. Bengio, and G. Hinton, "Deep learning," *nature*, vol. 521, no. 7553, pp. 436–444, 2015.
- [4] X. Peng, Q. Xu, Z. Feng, H. Zhao, L. Tan, Y. Zhou, Z. Zhang, C. Gong, and Y. Zheng, "Automatic news generation and fact-checking system based on language processing," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2405.10492*, 2024.
- [5] Y. Zhao and H. Gao, "Utilizing large language models for information extraction from real estate transactions," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2404.18043*, 2024.
- [6] Y. Zhao and F. Liu, "A survey of retrieval algorithms in ad and content recommendation systems," Jun 2024. [Online]. Available: osf.io/u59pd
- [7] L. Wang, Y. Cheng, A. Xiang, J. Zhang, and H. Yang, "Application of natural language processing in financial risk detection," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2406.09765*, 2024.
- [8] G. Han, W. Liu, X. Huang, and B. Borsari, "Chain-of-interaction: Enhancing large language models for psychiatric behavior understanding by dyadic contexts," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2403.13786*, 2024.
- [9] Y. Mo, H. Qin, Y. Dong, Z. Zhu, and Z. Li, "Large language model (llm) ai text generation detection based on transformer deep learning algorithm," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2405.06652*, 2024.
- [10] H. Jiang, F. Qin, J. Cao, Y. Peng, and Y. Shao, "Recurrent neural network from adder's perspective: Carry-lookahead rnn," *Neural Networks*, vol. 144, pp. 297–306, 2021.
- [11] K. Li, A. Zhu, W. Zhou, P. Zhao, J. Song, and J. Liu, "Utilizing deep learning to optimize software development processes," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2404.13630*, 2024.
- [12] Y. Cheng, Q. Yang, L. Wang, A. Xiang, and J. Zhang, "Research on credit risk early warning model of commercial banks based on neural network algorithm," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2405.10762*, 2024.
- [13] W. Lyu, S. Zheng, H. Ling, and C. Chen, "Backdoor attacks against transformers with attention enhancement," in *ICLR 2023 Workshop on Backdoor Attacks and Defenses in Machine Learning*, 2023.
- [14] W. Lyu, X. Lin, S. Zheng, L. Pang, H. Ling, S. Jha, and C. Chen, "Task-agnostic detector for insertion-based backdoor attacks," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2403.17155*, 2024.
- [15] K. O'shea and R. Nash, "An introduction to convolutional neural networks," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1511.08458*, 2015.
- [16] S. R. Dubey, S. K. Singh, and B. B. Chaudhuri, "Activation functions in deep learning: A comprehensive survey and benchmark," *Neurocomputing*, vol. 503, pp. 92–108, 2022.
- [17] C. Jin, T. Huang, Y. Zhang, M. Pechenizkiy, S. Liu, S. Liu, and T. Chen, "Visual prompting upgrades neural network sparsification: A data-model perspective," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2312.01397*, 2023.
- [18] Y. Gong, H. Qiu, X. Liu, Y. Yang, and M. Zhu, "Research and application of deep learning in medical image reconstruction and enhancement," *Frontiers in Computing and Intelligent Systems*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 72–76, 2024.
- [19] S. Liu, K. Yan, F. Qin, C. Wang, R. Ge, K. Zhang, J. Huang, Y. Peng, and J. Cao, "Infrared image super-resolution via lightweight information split network," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2405.10561*, 2024.
- [20] Y. Yang, H. Qiu, Y. Gong, X. Liu, Y. Lin, and M. Li, "Application of computer deep learning model in diagnosis of pulmonary nodules," 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2406.13205>
- [21] S. Melmed, "Pathogenesis of pituitary tumors," *Nature Reviews Endocrinology*, vol. 7, no. 5, pp. 257–266, 2011.
- [22] R. A. Buerki, C. M. Horbinski, T. Kruser, P. M. Horowitz, C. D. James, and R. V. Lukas, "An overview of meningiomas," *Future Oncology*, vol. 14, no. 21, pp. 2161–2177, 2018.
- [23] Y. Jiang and L. Uhrbom, "On the origin of glioma," *Upsala journal of medical sciences*, vol. 117, no. 2, pp. 113–121, 2012.
- [24] M. Sandler, A. Howard, M. Zhu, A. Zhmoginov, and L.-C. Chen, "Mobilenetv2: Inverted residuals and linear bottlenecks," in *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, 2018, pp. 4510–4520.
- [25] M. Tan and Q. Le, "Efficientnet: Rethinking model scaling for convolutional neural networks," in *International conference on machine learning*. PMLR, 2019, pp. 6105–6114.
- [26] K. He, X. Zhang, S. Ren, and J. Sun, "Deep residual learning for image recognition," in *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, 2016, pp. 770–778.
- [27] K. Simonyan and A. Zisserman, "Very deep convolutional networks for large-scale image recognition," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1409.1556*, 2014.
- [28] M. Nickparvar, "Brain tumor mri dataset," 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.kaggle.com/dsv/2645886>
- [29] H. Zhao, Y. Lou, Q. Xu, Z. Feng, Y. Wu, T. Huang, L. Tan, and Z. Li, "Optimization strategies for self-supervised learning in the use of unlabeled data," *Journal of Theory and Practice of Engineering Science*, vol. 4, no. 05, pp. 30–39, 2024.
- [30] C. Jin, T. Che, H. Peng, Y. Li, and M. Pavone, "Learning from teaching regularization: Generalizable correlations should be easy to imitate," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2402.02769*, 2024.
- [31] C. M. Bishop, "Pattern recognition and machine learning," *Springer google schola*, vol. 2, pp. 1122–1128, 2006.